

**STAGES OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND DIFFERENT
APPROACHES TO THEIR KNOWLEDGE**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotning turli bosqichlarini va ularni o'rganishdagi turlicha yondashuvlarni tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotning tarixiy va nazariy asoslari, rivojlanish jarayonlarining o'ziga xosligi, shu bilan birga, zamonaviy ijtimoiy tizimlarning shakllanishi va o'sishi muhim jihatlari sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada iqtisodiy inqiloblar, texnologik o'zgarishlar, jamiyat tuzilmalari o'rtasidagi bog'liqliklar, shuningdek, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tizimlarni o'rganishda ilgari surilgan yondashuvlar va metodologiyalar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyot, bosqichlar, rivojlanish, nazariy yondashuvlar, iqtisodiy inqiloblar, texnologik o'zgarishlar, ijtimoiy tizim, tahlil.

Abstract: This article is aimed at analyzing different stages of socio-economic development and different approaches to their study. The historical and theoretical foundations of socio-economic development, the uniqueness of development processes, as well as the formation and growth of modern social systems are considered as important aspects. The article analyzes economic revolutions, technological changes, connections between the structures of society, as well as approaches and methodologies advanced in the study of socio-economic systems.

Key words: socio-economic development, stages, mechanism, theoretical productions, economic revolutions, technological changes, social system, analysis.

Аннотация: Данная статья направлена на анализ различных этапов социально-экономического развития и разных подходов к их изучению. В качестве важных аспектов рассматриваются исторические и теоретические основы социально-экономического развития, своеобразие процессов развития, а также формирование и рост современных социальных систем. В статье анализируются экономические революции, технологические изменения, связи

между структурами общества, а также подходы и методологии, продвигаемые в исследовании социально-экономических систем.

***Ключевые слова:** социально-экономическое развитие, этапы, развитие, теоретические подходы, экономические революции, технологические изменения, социальная система, анализ.*

Introduction: The study of socio-economic development is a historically complex process. It is closely related to the cultural, economic and political changes of the society. Within this topic, various stages of the development process and existing approaches to their study have an important place. Interrelationships between the growth of societies, technological development, and economic systems require new approaches in each historical period. Therefore, there is an increasing need to study economic and social systems, to study existing theoretical approaches to the analysis of their development stages.

Literature review: There are many scientific works on the theoretical foundations of socio-economic development. Many scientists in this field have put forward different approaches. For example, Karl Marx bases the development of socio-economic systems on the class struggle and economic base. Max Weber distinguished cultural factors, religious and ideological factors in socio-economic development. Currently, methods of studying the process of formation and change of socio-economic development in various macro and micro economic models are widespread. Also, the processes of globalization are creating new approaches to this topic.

Classical approaches:

One of the first approaches to socio-economic development is related to the teachings of classical economic schools. Scientists such as Adam Smith, David Ricardo, Karl Marx and Max Weber describe the individual stages of socio-economic development in their works and explain how each of these stages causes economic and social changes.

Adam Smith's "Wealth of Nations" defined economic progress as natural growth. He expected economic growth from free activity of market forces and efficient work of labor force. And David Ricardo in his work "Teachings and Political Economy" emphasizes the need for changes in both social and economic conditions for economic development to be effective.

2. Modern approaches

Approaches to the understanding of socio-economic development in modern economic theories are more integrated and in many ways studied on a global scale.

Among these approaches, the stages of socio-economic development are explained in an evolutionary, revolutionary, and synergetic way.

Joseph Schumpeter is one of the scientists who developed the theory of innovation and economic growth. He called economic development a "creative process" and emphasized that the introduction of new technologies, access to new markets, and new production methods are the main factors of development. According to Schumpeter, economic systems can always undergo revolutionary changes.

3. Theory of stages

Ideas about the stages of socio-economic development have appeared in many scientific works. For example, Walt Rostow's "Stages of Economic Growth" proposed the division of development into five stages: 1) Traditional society, 2) Pre-conditions, 3) Progress of economic growth, 4) Rise, 5) Good standard of living. According to Rostow, every society must go through these stages in its development, which is an important condition for economic development.

Also, scientists who developed an evolutionary model of socio-economic development (for example, Talcott Parsons) considered the development process as a series of changes, decisions and social structural adaptations.

Opinion and comments: The topic of the stages of socio-economic development and different approaches to their knowledge is wide and complex and includes several directions, both historically and theoretically. In this field, there are differences between different disciplines (economics, sociology, history) and scientific schools, and each approach offers its own theoretical foundations and methods.

1. Stages of socio-economic development

When talking about the stages of socio-economic development, it is necessary to consider historical development processes and economic, political and cultural changes of societies. One of the most common approaches is the approach based on historical materialism, which emphasizes that the change and development of societies consists of several stages. In this approach, the development of society is seen in two main stages:

1. The initial stages are the era of feudalism and agrarian societies. At this stage, economic activity is formed mainly on the basis of agriculture and raw material production.

2. Next stages - Industrial revolution, capitalism and information society. During this period, the development of science and technology, the rise of production, and the expansion of the concept of private property bring about major changes.

Scientific approaches to the stages of socio-economic development provide different theoretical approaches to understanding societies. Choosing a direction

among these approaches is very complicated. For example, the difference between modernization and decolonization approaches shows that economic growth is not only related to technological progress and also needs to take into account social equality. Changes in the process of socio-economic development differ based on the needs and historical characteristics of different societies.

Also, in evaluating the effect of socio-economic development, it is necessary to take into account not only economic growth, but also factors such as social stability and environmental stability. That is, the economic development of society should include its cultural, political and ecological changes.

The above points show the importance and significance of different approaches to socio-economic development. Understanding the differences, interdependencies, and balances between these approaches is necessary to gain a complete picture of how societies progress.

Conclusion: In short, the stages of socio-economic development and different approaches to their study help to understand the development process more deeply. These approaches are interrelated and combine different methodological approaches to better understand societal change and development.

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